

HIGH TEMPERATURE DEFORMATION BEHAVIOR OF NANOCRYSTALLINE SiC/C COMPOSITE

Yutaka Shinoda¹, Hui Gu¹ and Fumihiro Wakai²

¹ *Japan Science and Technology Corporation, ICORP "Ceramics Superplasticity",
JFCC 2F, 2-4-1 Mutsuno, Atsuta-ku, Nagoya 456-8587, Japan*

² *Center for Materials Design, Materials and Structures Laboratory, Tokyo Institute of
Technology, 4259 Nagatsuta, Midori-ku, Yokohama 226-8503, Japan*

SUMMARY: Nanocrystalline silicon carbide/carbon (SiC/C) composite was fabricated from ultrafine SiC powder containing 3.5 wt% free carbon by ultra-high pressure hot isostatic pressing (HIP) at a pressure of 980 MPa and a temperature of 1600 °C. The average SiC grain size of the composite was 30 nm, and the carbon existed at SiC grain boundary as excess carbon or as graphite layer. The high temperature deformation behavior of this material was investigated by a tensile test at the temperatures from 1800 to 2000 °C at the initial strain rates from 1×10^{-5} to 1×10^{-4} s⁻¹. The nanocrystalline SiC/C composite exhibited extremely high strength and high ductility at elevated temperature.

KEYWORDS: nanocrystalline, silicon carbide, mechanical property, superplasticity, grain growth

INTRODUCTION

SiC is covalent material with strong interatomic bonding. It is therefore that the hardness and high temperature strength of SiC is extremely high. However SiC is poor in ductility even at high temperatures. Grain refinement is one of the most effective way to improve the ductility at elevated temperatures and has brought about superplasticity of many metals, alloys or ceramics[1-2]. For superplastic deformation not only the grain size has to be fine, but also the microstructure has to be stable at elevated temperatures. SiC is hard to densify because of its covalent nature, and so sintering additives as metal or metal oxide are added for densification.[3-4] However, these additives occasionally lead to degradation of strength at high temperature.[5] These additives tend to promote grain growth at elevated temperature also [6], and so it is too difficult to obtain nanocrystalline SiC with high temperature stability. SiC/C composite is expected that the fine grain microstructure is stable and the strength is high at high temperatures. It is important that homogeneous dispersion of a small amount of carbon through SiC bulk to keep excellent features of SiC as hardness and high temperature strength. The importance of homogeneous dispersion of carbon increases with grain refinement, but in practical the dispersion becomes difficult with decreasing grain size. Here we tried

fabrication of nanocrystalline SiC/C composite from ultrafine SiC powder containing fine free carbon homogeneously and investigated its high temperature deformation behavior.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Preparation of Sample

Ultrafine β -SiC powder was prepared by gas phase reaction of SiCl_4 , SiH_4 , CH_4 and C_2H_4 (Sumitomo-Osaka Cement Co., Tokyo, Japan, T-1 grade). The mean particle size measured by using a transmission electron microscope (TEM) was 30 nm and the surface area analyzed by BET method was $48.0 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$. The powder contained 3.7 wt% free carbon and 0.41 wt% oxygen and the amount of another metallic impurities was less than 1 ppm. The powder was die-pressed at a pressure of 40 MPa into rectangular bars of $10 \text{ mm} \times 12 \text{ mm} \times 48 \text{ mm}$. After cold-isostatic-pressing (CIP) under 200 MPa, the powder compact was glass vacuum encapsulated with Pyrex glass tube (Iwaki Glass Co., Chiba, Japan) at about $760 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The compact had been coated with BN powder (Syowa Denko Co., Tokyo, Japan, UH-1 grade) before CIP to prevent it from reacting with a glass tube. The capsules were heated with a heating rate of $13 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ and kept for 20 min at $800 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in Ar atmosphere. Afterwards the pressure was increased up to 980 MPa at a rate of 13 MPa/min. At the pressure of 180 MPa the temperature was increased again. The temperature and the pressure were kept constant at $1600 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and 980 MPa respectively for 1 h.

Microstructure

For the microstructural observation of sintered body by scanning electron microscopy (SEM), the sintered body was cut and polished and then buffed with diamond past of $1 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ in particle size. Subsequently the specimens were etched with Murakami solution. For transmission electron microscopy (TEM) and EELS analysis, the sample was ground and polished into a $\phi 3 \text{ mm}$ disk with the thickness of $50 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ and buffed with diamond past of $1 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ in particle size. Then the specimen was thinned by an ion milling devise.

Mechanical Property

Tensile specimens were cut and ground into the shape shown in Fig.1 and then polished and buffed with diamond past of $1 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ in particle size. Tensile tests at a constant cross-head speed were conducted at the temperatures from 1800 to $2000 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ at the initial strain rate from 1×10^{-4} to $1 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$ in argon atmosphere.

Fig. 1: The tensile specimen

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 2 is SEM micrograph of SiC/C composite. The average SiC grain size was 60 nm. This means that grain growth during sintering was very slow. TEM observation and EELS analysis revealed that the free carbon existed as excess carbon and graphite layer at grain boundary of SiC. The relative density was about 97%.

Fig. 2: SEM micrograph of SiC/C composite

Figure 3 shows stress-strain curves of SiC/C composite at the temperatures from 1800 to 2000 °C at the initial strain rate of $1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ s}^{-1}$. The flow stress levels decreased and the ductility increased with increasing temperature. Generally the flow stress level at elevated temperatures decrease with decreasing grain size if deformation is governed by grain boundary sliding. However, despite the grain size was very fine, the flow stresses were extremely high and even at 2000 °C the steady stress was about 100 MPa. Figure 4 shows stress-strain curves of SiC/C composite at the temperatures of 1900 °C at the initial strain rate from 1×10^{-4} to $1 \times 10^{-5} \text{ s}^{-1}$. The strain rate dependence of flow stress was small and stress exponent was about 6. Usually superplastic ceramic materials exhibit stress exponent value of 2 to 3. Deformation mechanism of those superplastic materials is grain boundary sliding. The stress exponent of nanocrystalline SiC/C composite was much higher than those of superplastic materials. Those suggest that the deformation proceed by movement of transgranular dislocations. Although the deformation mechanism differ from that of superplastic materials, the ductility were relatively high. It was supposed that extremely fine grain and its stability at high temperature which reduced stress concentration made possible such high ductility. In this way, it was shown that nanocrystalline SiC/C composite containing carbon dispersed homogeneously was promising as high temperature structural material because of its high temperature strength and ductility.

Fig. 3: Temperature dependence of stress-strain curves

Fig. 4: Initial strain rate dependence of stress-strain curves

CONCLUSIONS

Nanocrystalline SiC/C composite with average SiC grain size of 30 nm was fabricated by ultra-high pressure HIP. SiC/C composite exhibited extremely high strength even at the temperature over 1800 °C, and exhibited high ductility due to stability of the fine grain microstructure at high temperature.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors would like to thank Dr. Isao Tanaka for kindly having let us use the devices for glass vacuum encapsulating.

REFERENCES

1. Edington, J. W., Melton, K. N. and Cutler, C. P., "Superplasticity", *Prog. Mater. Sci.*, 1976, pp. 61-170.
5. Chen, I. W. and Xue, L. A. "Development of superplastic structural ceramics", *Journal of American Ceramic Society*, Vol. 73, 1990, pp. 2585-2609.
3. Alliegro, R.A., Coffin, L.B. and Tinklepaugh, J.R., "Pressure-Sintered Silicon Carbide", *Journal of American Ceramic Society*, Vol. 39, No. 11, 1956, pp. 386-389.
4. Prochazka, S., "Sintering of Silicon Carbide", *Ceramics for High Performance Applications*, Edited by Burke, J.J., Gorum, A.E. and Kats, R.N. Brook Hill Pub. Co., Chestnut Hill, Mass., 1974, pp. 239.
5. Shinoda, Y., Nagano, T. and Wakai, F., "Fabrication of Nanograined Silicon Carbide by Ultrahigh-Pressure Hot Isostatic Pressing", *Journal of American Ceramic Society*, Vol. 82, No. 3, 1999, pp.771-773.
6. Nagano, T., Honda, S., Wakai, F. and Mitomo, M., "Compressive deformation of liquid-phase sintered silicon carbide at elevated temperature", *Proceedings of the Superplasticity and Superplastic Forming*, The Minerals, Metal & Materials Society, Edited by Ghosh, A.K. and Bieler, T.R. 1998, pp. 247-255.